

Harmful Algae News

AN IOC NEWSLETTER ON TOXIC ALGAE AND ALGAL BLOOMS

No. 82 – March 2026 · <https://hab.ioc-unesco.org/>

IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Microalgae: Cyanobacteria Updates

The IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Microalgae is a globally recognised catalogue and website (<https://marinespecies.org/hab/>) developed under the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) that lists the names of microalgal species (including cyanobacteria) known to produce toxins or cause harmful effects in aquatic environments. The list aims to promote taxonomic stability in support of monitoring, management, and research activities.

The list currently (December 2025) includes 122 dinoflagellates, 99 cyanobacteria, 31 diatoms, 8 haptophytes, 5 raphidophytes, and 3 dictyochophytes (Fig. 1).

The cyanobacterial editors have actively updated the cyanobacterial section to incorporate toxic species from both marine and freshwater environments. This ongoing effort reflects the increasing ecological and socio-economic importance of cyanobacteria in freshwater, coastal and estuarine systems, where climate-driven bloom expansion is enhancing their impact [1–2].

Cyanobacteria are remarkable for their diversity and their ability to occupy a wide range of ecological niches. They play a crucial ecological role as producers of oxygen. Some taxa are also key biological nitrogen fixers, act-

ing either as free-living diazotrophs or as symbionts in diatom–diazotroph associations that sustain primary production in oligotrophic marine environments. Cyanobacterial symbionts are also found in association with dinoflagellates, and recent research on the dinoflagellate *Ornithocercus* has revealed genetically diverse, yet host-specific, cyanobiont assemblages in temperate coastal waters [3].

However, certain cyanobacteria are problematic as they form dense, harmful blooms and produce potent cyanotoxins, which pose serious risks to aquatic ecosystems and human health (e.g., [4]) (Fig. 2). The frequency and duration of cyanobacterial blooms have increased globally along with heightened anthropogenic nutrient loading associated with population growth and land-use change, as well as climate change (e.g., [5]). *Raphidiopsis raciborskii* (formerly *Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii*) is one of the most widely documented cyanobacterial species whose expansion has been linked to global environmental change (e.g., [6]).

Cyanobacteria produce toxins known as cyanotoxins, the most well-known of which are neurotoxins, hepatotoxins, dermatotoxins and cytotoxins. These toxins can harm or even kill humans and animals (e.g., [7]). Depending on species and environmental context, cyanobacterial blooms may be associated with elevated cyanotoxin production. Exposure to cyanobacterial toxins during harmful algal blooms in marine or freshwater environments can result in diseases affecting the liver, nervous system or skin in humans and animals. This exposure can occur through the ingestion of contaminated water, dermal contact (e.g., during swimming), inhalation of aerosols, and consumption of seafood or crops irrigated with contaminated water [8]. The link between

Fig. 1. Proportional representation of 268 taxa included in the IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Microalgae.

unesco

Intergovernmental
Oceanographic
Commission

Content

UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Microalgae: Cyanobacteria Updates	1
--	---

HAB events and prediction

HAB species in the Seaflower Biosphere Reserve, San Andrés Island, Colombian Caribbean.....	4
New Machine Learning-Based tool (CyFi) to monitor inland water Bodies	6

Networking and Coordination

ICES-IOC Workshop on automated imaging of plankton.....	8
ANZ HABNET, community response to unprecedented HAB events in South Australia, 2025–2026.....	10
MedHab Technical Workshop on One Health in the Mediterranean	12
Call for Editor(s)-in-Chief for the Next Global HAB Status Report.....	14

IOC Courses 2026

IRTA-IOC International Intercomparison (IPI) Test	16
IOC HAB Identification Qualification.....	16

Forthcoming Events

13 th Dino (Modern and Fossil Dinoflagellates) Conference, 5–10 July 2026, Bremen, Germany)	17
2026 Global eDNA Conference, October 28–30, 2026, Seattle, USA...	17
International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety, 6–11 September, Exeter, UK	18
Prof. F.J.R. (“Max”) Taylor obituary..	19

Fig. 2. Cyanobacterial blooms illustrating environmental pressure in aquatic systems. (A) *Microcystis aeruginosa* bloom in Magos reservoir, Portugal; (B) sample from the *M. aeruginosa* bloom; (C) *M. aeruginosa* macroscopic colonies in the Magos reservoir; (D) *M. aeruginosa* bloom in a lake near Hillerød, Denmark; (E, F) *Aphanizomenon* sp. in a lake in the Paris area, France; (G) *Limnospira* sp. in the lake Dziani Dzaha of Mayotte, France; (H) *Planktothrix* sp. in a lake of the Paris area, France; (I) *Trichodesmium erythraeum* in the channel linking Bazaruto to Pomene, Inhambane, Mozambique. Photos are courtesy of C. Bernard, MNHN and C. Churro, IPMA.

climate change, environmental contamination, population growth, cyanotoxin production, and disease are now well established (e.g., [9, 5]).

Due to the increasing number of genomic sequences of cyanobacteria, the availability of well-described reference strains, and the establishment of standardised workflows for describing new taxa, cyanobacterial taxonomy is currently undergoing a period of rapid change [10]. The most recent major update to cyanobacterial classification at the order and family levels was introduced by Komárek et al. [11, 12], based on a polyphasic approach. In 2023, Strunecky et al. proposed a robust phylogenomic framework for taxonomic purposes, integrating genome-based phylogenies with traditional polyphasic descriptions of type species and corresponding genera across the Cyanobacteria phylum. According to this classification, cyanobacterial genera are currently assigned to 19 orders [10].

Like other bacteria, cyanobacteria exhibit high plasticity and substantial genotypic diversity, not only between species but also within a given genus, and particularly at the strain level. From an ecological perspective, this microdiversity is essential for marine or freshwater cyanobacterial populations, enabling them to cope with spatio-temporal environmental variability and to adapt to specific micro-niches within ecosystems.

However, this aspect of intraspecific diversity is often overlooked in studies of bloom development or the relationship between cyanobacterial species and toxicity (e.g., [13, 14]). Further-

Fig. 3. Proportional representation of (A) cyanobacterial orders that include toxic taxa (10 of the 19 currently recognised orders) and (B) cyanobacterial toxins produced by the 99 cyanobacterial taxa included in the IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Microalgae (December 2025).

more, genome comparisons among individuals within monospecific blooms have revealed considerable heterogeneity in gene content, despite similar genome sizes and high similarity indices. These differences are mainly associated with mobile genetic elements and biosynthetic gene clusters. Metabolomic analyses have confirmed corresponding heterogeneity in the production of secondary metabolites, including cyanotoxins, and the harmful consequences of this heterogeneity (e.g., [15]). Consequently, within a single cyanobacterial species, toxic and non-toxic strains may coexist, as well as multitoxic strains carrying multiple functional toxin biosynthetic gene clusters.

Considering this microdiversity at the species and strain levels, the cyanobacterial editorial committee considers the following attributes for the updated list of toxic cyanobacteria:

- The list is based on publications documenting harmful effects associated with cyanobacterial isolates/strains or natural blooms dominated by a cyanobacterial species.
- Environmental conditions may selectively favour toxic or non-toxic genotypes within a species due to underlying microdiversity.
- Attribution of toxicity in environmental samples to the dominant species should be interpreted with caution until confirmation using isolated and characterised strains is available.

As of 2025, the list includes 99 cyanobacterial taxa, of which 62 are freshwater and 32 marine, representing 33% and 12%, respectively, of the total toxic taxa included in the list. Among the newly described species is *Okeanomitocorallinicola*, a marine heterocyte-forming cyanobacterium isolated from coral reefs [16]. Remarkably, this species produces 13 classes of microcystins and exhibits cytotoxic activity against cancer cell lines. Another notable microcystin producer is *Aliinostoc bakau* [17], highlighting that microcystin production in marine environments may be more widespread than previously thought.

Recent updates also include newly described toxins and novel effects on other organisms. For example, *Aetokthonos hydrillicola* produces aetokthonotoxin (AETX), colloquially known as the “eagle toxin”, identified in 2021 as

the causative agent of Avian Vacuolar Myelinopathy (AVM) in North American eagles [18]. Another notable class of toxic compounds are spumigins, protease inhibitors with pharmaceutical relevance, reported in 2015 from *Sphaerospermopsis torques-reginae*. Spumigin congeners are inhibitors of serine and cysteine proteases and may have applications in drug development.

Of the 19 cyanobacterial orders currently recognised, 10 include toxic species. The order with the highest proportion of toxic taxa is Nostocales (43%), followed by Oscillatoriales (20%), and Chroococcales (17%) (Fig. 3A). In terms of toxin prevalence, microcystins remain the most widely produced compounds, associated with 55 taxa. Saxitoxins and anatoxins follow, with 17 and 15 producers, respectively, occurring in both benthic and planktonic taxa. Other toxins include cylindrospermopsins (12 taxa), nodularins (10 taxa), β -N-methylamino-L-alanine (BMAA) (23 taxa), and its co-occurring isomers DAB and AEG. Less frequently reported toxins include spumigins (one taxon), guanitoxin (anatoxin-a(S)) (five taxa), homoanatoxin-a (four taxa), aplysiatoxins (three taxa), lyngbyatoxin (two taxa) and aetokthonotoxin (one taxon) (Fig. 3B).

Nevertheless, caution is warranted when interpreting toxin production in widespread species such as *Prochlorococcus marinus* (linked to BMAA) and *Pseudanabaena limnetica* (linked to anatoxin-a). These taxa are globally distributed in marine and freshwater environments, respectively, and their ecological roles—particularly that of *Prochlorococcus* as a globally dominant picocyanobacterium—strongly suggests that toxin production is strain-specific and/or context-dependent.

In conclusion, the description of new toxic cyanobacterial species and advances in cyanobacterial taxonomy demonstrate that the diversity of these microorganisms remains substantially under-described, and that their functional roles within ecosystems are still only partially understood.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the editors of the IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Microalgae.

References

1. Dhillon J & Parker ER 2025. *JAAD Rev* 4:156–166. doi.org/10.1016/j.jdrv.2025.02.012
2. Fraga M et al 2025. *Mar Pollut Bull* 216:118017. doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2025.118017.
3. Kim M et al 2021. *Sci Rep* 11, 9458. doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-89072-z.
4. Huisman J et al 2018. *Nat Rev Microbiol* 16:471–483. doi.org/10.1038/s41579-018-00401
5. Paerl HW & Paul VJ 2012. *Water Res* 46:1349–1363. doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2011.08.002
6. Kokociński M et al 2017. *FEMS Microbiol Ecol* 93:fix035. doi.org/10.1093/femsec/fix035.
7. Nugumanova G et al 2023. *Toxins* 15:233. doi.org/10.3390/toxins15030233.
8. Miller A & Russell C 2017. *Environ Health Rev* 60:58–63. doi.org/10.5864/d2017-021.
9. Watt C et al 2021. *Water* 13:3151. doi.org/10.3390/w13223151.
10. Strunecký et al 2023. *J Phycology*, 59(1):12–51. doi.org/10.1080/00318884.2025.2603640.
11. Komárek J et al 2014. *Preslia* 86:295–335. doi.org/10.23855/preslia.2014.295.
12. Komárek J 2020. *Fottea* 20:104–110. doi.org/10.5507/fot.2019.020.
13. Halary S et al 2023. *ISME Commun.* doi.org/10.1038/s43705-023-00263-3.
14. Mirte C et al 2025. doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2024.2520.
15. Roussel T et al. 2025. *Microbiology spectrum*. doi.org/10.1128/spectrum.01901-24.
16. Li H et al 2024. *J Phycol* 60:908–927. doi.org/10.1111/jpy.13473.
17. Merican F et al 2024. *Diversity* 16:22. doi.org/10.3390/d16010022.
18. Breinlinger S et al., *Science* 371. doi.org/10.1126/science.aax9050.

Authors

Cécile Bernard, UMR Molécules de Communication et Adaptation des Microorganismes MNHN-CNRS, Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, 75005 Paris, France.

Catarina Churro, IPMA, Portuguese Institute for the Sea and Atmosphere, Algas, Portugal & CIIMAR, Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research, University of Porto, Matosinhos, Portugal.

Nina Lundholm, Natural History Museum Denmark, University of Copenhagen, Denmark.

Kenneth Mertens, Ifremer, COAST, F-29900 Concarneau, France.

Email corresponding author: cecile.bernard@mnhn.fr

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19045656>